

HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-01
European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking

Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations CoE
101093261

D1.7

Initial assessment of developments and revision of the scientific challenges - Enabling Next-Generation Plasma Accelerators for Real World Applications with PIConGPU

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

Date of preparation (latest version): 31/12/2023
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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable Number	D1.7
Deliverable Name	Initial assessment of developments and revision of the scientific challenges - Enabling Next-Generation Plasma Accelerators for Real World Applications with PIConGPU
Due Date	31/12/2023
Deliverable lead	HZDR
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Keywords	laser-plasma interaction, laser-plasma accelerators PIConGPU, alpaka, openPMD, TWEAC
WP/Task	WP1/Task D1.7
Nature	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Final Version Date	31/12/2023
Reviewed by	Vassilis Papaefstathiou (FORTH) and Tilman Dannert (MPG)

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Partner	Date	Comment	Version
HZDR	10/10/2023	First draft	0.1
HDZR	01/12/2023	Final draft	0.2
KTH	04/12/2023	Final draft updated for internal review	0.3
HZDR	11/12/2023	Final draft updated after 1st review	0.4
HZDR	14/12/2023	Final draft updated after 2nd review	0.5
HZDR	15/12/2023	Revised Final draft after all internal reviews	0.6
KTH	18/12/2023	Final cleanup for submission	1.0

Executive Summary

PIConGPU has recently demonstrated the envisioned Figures-of-Merit (FOM) for Plasma-PEPSC on the Oak Ridge National Laboratory Frontier system, which was reported at the 2023 Supercomputing Conference. This is an indication that we will be reaching at least similar performance on JUPITER at Forschungszentrum Jülich but we expect adaption to the European exascale compute architectures for both the alpaka library and PIConGPU to reach the FOM on JUPITER.

We produced first results for both ARM and RISC-V architectures with the full PIConGPU simulation code using realistic simulation setups for the Weibe and Kelvin-Helmholtz instability respectively, including scaling tests. It is clear from these tests that autovectorization by compilers is not reliable and work needs to be done to better support vectorization of PIConGPU code. For this we will explore what changes would be necessary in both PIConGPU and alpaka to achieve this.

The physics case for the funding period will need further investigation as the current laser model does not yet allow to investigate energy efficient acceleration. This is subject to further investigation and we will thus first focus on less efficient scenarios to understand the fundamental acceleration mechanism.

The most critical part of the project is the limitation of modern file systems in terms of throughput compared to the data stream of PByte / min scale produced in an optimized PIConGPU simulation. We will thus further investigate streaming data analytics, in-situ visualization and intelligent online data reduction as key elements to maximize the scientific output of exascale simulations.

In summary, we do not see any significant deviations from our original work plan.

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1 Introduction

Laser-plasma interaction at Petawatt laser class level is a frontier technology with a uniquely broad range of applications from accelerator physics, the study of laser-driven fusion, medical applications such as tumor therapy, the development of bright and compact free electron lasers to the study fundamental astrophysical phenomena in the laboratory. In the Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations Center of Excellence we will study a new accelerator technology, Traveling-Wave Electron Acceleration (TWEAC), using PIConGPU. TWEAC has the potential to provide a scalable acceleration scheme towards ultra-brilliant, high quality electron beams at the TeV energy scale.

Scalability of PIConGPU towards the Exascale has been demonstrated recently at the Frontier supercomputer at Oak Ridge National Laboratory. Thus our focus is to make optimum use of upcoming hardware accelerator technologies used within EuroHPC and provided by the European Processor Initiative (EPI).

PIConGPU utilizes the portable parallel programming library alpaka [1, 2] to achieve single source heterogeneous computing. The goal of optimally using upcoming hardware will be achieved by developing and fine-tuning a backend for the alpaka library for EPI hardware. To evaluate the performance of PIConGPU on current and future computer architectures, we have defined a figure of merit as the weighted sum of the total number of particle updates per second (90 %) and the number of cell updates per second (10 %), since this ratio corresponds to the most time-consuming part of the particle-in-cell algorithm. We present this figure of merit current scaling on top 10 high performance computer systems such as Summit and Frontier.

At Exascale performance, the follow-up challenge for the PIConGPU team will be to analyze, visualize and further reuse the data from high quality simulations, e.g. for AI/ML-driven surrogate models. For this, we plan to further develop the openPMD API and strengthen the openPMD ecosystem. With PIConGPU as the central application for laser-plasma interaction studies in Helmholtz, further development in the capabilities of the code to predict the outcome of laser-plasma interaction experiments and develop applications is key to a successful research program. This goes hand in hand with enabling PIConGPU to make optimum use of future European Exascale systems.

Furthermore, data-intense workflows for efficient checkpointing, Exascale I/O and in-memory code coupling using the openPMD ecosystem will be investigated to make optimum use of the data produced at future European exascale systems.

2 Revision of the Scientific Challenge

The initial report D1.3 defined the scientific challenges as follows.

2.1 Physics challenges

- Identify the most suitable TWEAC regimes for stable acceleration.
- Demonstrate acceleration of electrons in a single stage beyond 10 GeV with TWEAC.
- Assess which injection techniques of standard Laser-Plasma Accelerators (LPAs) can be employed for TWEAC.

- Evaluate possibilities for injection of high-brightness electrons.
- Explore new capabilities of TWEAC with respect to electron injection techniques.

As our scientific goal did not change, these challenges are up-to-date. However, due to our ongoing work on the TWEAC scheme, we have identified one further challenge:

- Identify TWEAC regimes where the laser pulse can be modelled with existing methods

Since the beginning of the project, we had to realize that modelling of the laser pulse in small interaction angle regimes with perpendicular polarization of the incident laser pulses cannot be done with the existing methods. Due to the tight focusing and long propagation distances of the laser pulse within the simulation volume in small interaction angle regimes, accurate vector modelling of the laser pulse, which takes weak laser components into account, is of importance. Otherwise the laser plasma interaction yields non-physical plasma dynamics.

We thus aim for large interaction angle regimes of TWEAC initially, since these are easier to model for two reasons. First, the time within which a slice of the laser pulse stays in the simulated volume reduces. This reduces accumulation of errors. Second, large interaction angle regimes can be realized with parallel polarized laser pulses which probably can be modelled with existing methods to sufficient accuracy. During the project time we will further investigate the small angle case towards its feasibility for simulation with the goal to find a suitable model description.

2.2 Computational resources and numerical challenges

- Long-term stability: Simulations of TWEAC beyond 10 GeV will run of the order of 10^6 timesteps. Stability of the solvers, in terms of artificial amplification of noise or small errors, needs to be studied.
- Accuracy: If stability of the simulation setup is given, we want to ensure high-fidelity simulation results, i. e. keep errors due to numerical inaccuracies low. We will use higher order schemes for the solvers, i. e. field solver, particle pusher, and particle shape. These schemes are already implemented.
- Simulation volume size: Due to the line focus geometry, the laser pulses used in TWEAC have a large width in the plane transverse to the focal plane compared to the cylindrical symmetric laser pulses used in standard Laser-Wakefield Accelerators (LWFAs). In order to capture the plasma cavity formation correctly in the simulation, large plasma volumes have to be simulated. Together with the increased accuracy requirement, this increases the required computational resources by orders of magnitude compared to standard LWFA simulations.

As before, these challenge are still existing. Along the lines of the discussion on laser modelling in sec. 2.1, we add one item reflecting our effort to model laser pulses for small interaction angle geometries.

- Laser model accuracy: implement and test a cylindrical quasi-Gaussian vector beam

3 Summary of developments

3.1 Software Releases

In the past few months, new releases of both PIConGPU and alpaka were published on public Github repositories: <https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu> and <https://github.com/alpaka-group/alpaka>.

The PIConGPU release introduces significant enhancements to laser initialization processes, expanded physics support, and crucial bug fixes. The adoption of new features from C++17 necessitates an increase to minimum required C++ version of this release.

3.2 Provide scriptable PIConGPU interface (pyPIConGPU) for automatization

The latest release of PIConGPU incorporates basic Particle-In-Cell Modeling Interface (PICMI) support, which facilitates the streamlined definition of input files for PIC simulations through a Python interface. This not only enhances the code's usability but also contributes to a fully scriptable interface, known as pyPIConGPU, enabling automatization.

3.3 Performance-portability to novel European exascale compute architectures

3.3.1 PIConGPU runs on ARM

Utilizing the Wombat cluster at Oak Ridge National Laboratory PIConGPU had already been ported to ARM and first scaling tests have been conducted. Specifically, PIConGPU was executed on Ampere Altra CPUs with 80 cores. The results have been published in [3]. See D2.1 for details of the tests.

The main findings are recapitulated in the following.

- While the initial ARM porting was not part of this project, it will be the base for further tests of the ARM architecture using PIConGPU within the Plasma-PEPSC funding period.
- In order to run the test on the Ampere Altra CPUs, the existing OpenMP backend of alpaka was used. Therefore, no additional development work in alpaka was necessary to run PIConGPU on ARM.
- It is known that reliable and performant SIMD support will require a better interplay between alpaka and PIConGPU.

3.3.2 PIConGPU runs on RISC-V

As of November 2023, a demonstration run of PIConGPU on a RISC-V architecture was performed successfully on the ExCALIBUR H&ES RISC-V testbed at EPCC, University of Edinburgh, see D2.2 for details.

This was a first test to explore the RISC-V architecture. Similar to the ARM case above, we will explore better SIMD support in the coming project funding time. See below for more details on alpaka autovectorization support.

3.3.3 PICongGPU performed weak scaling on LUMI

A weak scaling of PICongGPU on LUMI with the PICongGPU TWEAC FOM example has been performed. The results are presented in fig. 1. PICongGPU shows perfect weak

Figure 1: (a) Weak scaling of PICongGPU from 8 to 2048 GCDs (Graphic Compute Dies) on Lumi using the TWEAC FOM benchmark with a Gaussian laser pulse. PICongGPU achieves a weak scaling efficiency $> 99\%$. (b) Corresponding FOM scaling. The orange line represents ideal scaling of the baseline measurement.

scaling with an efficiency larger than 99% from 8 to 2048 GCDs (Graphic Compute Dies), i. e. 1 to 256 nodes.

3.4 Test suite for continuous integration

PICongGPU already provides a basic continuous integration (CI) workflow, proving a suite of compilation tests that quickly detect code regressions in development. The CI tests however did not test code functionality or the fidelity of physics predictions. In an effort to fix this, unit tests for code functionality have been implemented and a first one is now added to the CI. Furthermore, we have added a number of run time tests with automatic evaluation of physics results to PICongGPU, see <https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu/tree/dev/share/picongpu/tests>. These are not yet automatically executed during CI runs, but it is planned to run these on a nightly or weekly base once the necessary hardware is available. We plan to restrict the resource requirement of these tests to one modern GPU with ~ 16 GiB on device memory and a maximum run time of a few minutes.

3.5 Develop, test and fine-tune alpaka backend for European exascale compute architecture

In order to perform the test run on RISC-V, we had to add a CMake toolchain to PICongGPU for cross-compiling on x86 architecture for RISC-V, see <https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu/pull/4712>. No development work was required in alpaka for this run.

From this initial test we see that auto-vectorization of nested loops (as used in PICongGPU) are a limiting factor to fully utilize vector units. This is a limitation due to compiler capabilities. We will explore what can be done in PICongGPU and alpaka to better aid vectorization.

Ongoing alpaka optimization for GPUs, e. g. adding support for unified memory which will provide a generic approach to utilize hierarchical memory architectures (<https://github.com/alpaka-group/alpaka/pull/2180>), is relevant for existing and upcoming GPU based exascale-class systems, such as LUMI and JUPITER.

4 Revision of Gap analysis

No updates compared to previous report. As reported earlier, PICongGPU met the FOM target on OLCF's Frontier system already and we thus expect similar performance on the JUPITER system at Jülich supercomputing center. Upcoming developments, with respect to the previously identified gaps, will focus on I/O workflows for the Tbyte to Pbyte scale which pose a significant challenge to handle the data produced by the code due to the widening bandwidth gap between the data stream produced by a highly optimized simulation and the throughput capabilities of existing file systems.

5 Revision of Roadmap

The initial report D1.3 defined the roadmap for development as follows.

1. Identification of Bottlenecks in the Current Code
 - 1.1. Performance-portability to novel European exascale compute architectures
 - 1.2. I/O capabilities to optimally exploit memory layouts of European exascale systems
 - 1.3. In-transit data analysis to tackle the data deluge
2. Test suite for continuous integration and code interface for automatization to secure fidelity of physics results in code development
3. Next Steps planned
 - 3.1. Extend, test and fine-tune I/O capabilities to optimally exploit memory capabilities in European exascale systems
 - 3.2. Extend and test streaming capability in PICongGPU using openPMD/ADIOS2 to be used in production

- 3.3. Provide test suite for continuous integration and provide scriptable PIConGPU interface (pyPIConGPU) for automatization
- 3.4. Develop, test and fine-tune alpaka backend for European exascale compute architectures

There has been work on several of the roadmap items as described in Section 3. There is no major revision and this roadmap is up-to-date.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, our work revolves around the simulation of Traveling-Wave Electron Acceleration (TWEAC) utilizing PIConGPU, aiming to achieve scalable acceleration for ultra-brilliant electron beams at the TeV energy scale. Notably, our efforts center on the scalability of PIConGPU and its I/O, leveraging alpaka for heterogeneous computing, and optimizing for upcoming hardware accelerator technologies, especially those advanced by the European Processor Initiative (EPI).

Scientific challenges, encompassing TWEAC regimes, electron acceleration beyond 10 GeV, injection techniques, and laser pulse modeling in specific interaction angle regimes, form the core of our research. Computational challenges, including stability, accuracy, and accommodating large simulation volumes, underscore the importance of preparing PIConGPU for forthcoming European Exascale systems.

Our recent developments showcase significant enhancements in PIConGPU and alpaka, demonstrating performance-portability on novel European exascale compute architectures like RISC-V, showcasing excellent weak scaling on LUMI and introducing a scriptable PIConGPU interface for automation. The ongoing establishment of a comprehensive test suite for continuous integration, featuring unit tests for code functionality and runtime tests for physics results, signifies our commitment to robust and reliable simulations.

The ongoing work on PIConGPU seats it in a prime position to face the computational challenges of laser-plasma interaction studies on upcoming European Exascale systems, with a further focus on fine-tuning execution and I/O on these systems and overcoming memory bandwidth limits using streaming.

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